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Apolinário, Isaías (1917–2000)

THE BRAZILIAN WHITE CENTER – UNASP

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Isaías Apolinário, businessman¹ and patron,² was born September 28, 1917, in Taubaté city, São Paulo state.³ He was the second son of Manoel Apolinário (1889-1974) and Tereza Ferreira Apolinário (1889-1975);⁴ an Adventist couple who was baptized on January 27, 1917, at the Brazilian Publishing House, in Santo André, São Paulo.⁵ His siblings were: Diná (1916-1971), Pedro (1919-2006),⁶ Ester (1920-2006), Amadeu (1922-2008), Rute (1923-2014), João (1925-2008) and Ruben Apolinário.⁷

For 13 years Isaías served at the Brazilian Publishing House in the Binding and Expedition Department. There he met Leonor Apolinário, whom he married on July 17, 1941. The couple had two children: Denise and Décio.⁸

When he left the Brazilian Publishing House he started his own business.⁹ In 1948 he worked at Grande ABC as a merchant in Santo André city. As time passed, his business increased and Isaías became a successful entrepreneur.¹⁰

Kind and generous, Isaías financed the construction of the Adventist school of Taubaté and also contributed financially to purchase the land for the construction of the Central Church and SDA School of Santo André, in São Paulo state. He sponsored the construction of Adventist churches in Santo André and Riacho Grande in the city of São Bernardo, and of the first church of Mauá, cities located in the São Paulo suburban area. He contributed to the construction of other churches in the cities of São Paulo and Rondônia states. Between 1950 and 1970, also subsidized radio transmission of the Voice of Prophecy program to some cities in the state of São Paulo.¹¹

With his wife by his side, Isaías spent the last years of his life in the peaceful city of Monte Azul Paulista, São Paulo state. There he died of cardiac complications on March 29, 2000. Isaías was buried in the cemetery of Vila Assunção, city of Santo André.¹²

By sharing God's blessings, Isaías helped to construct schools and churches and to produce evangelistic radio programs. He was a committed and enthusiastic donor who helped the progress of Adventism in Brazil in the second half of the 20th century.¹³

NOTES

1. Lessa, Rubens S., "Ânimo e fé durante o sequestro," *Revista Adventista*, year 87, no. 7, July 1991, 5.?
2. Décio Apolinário, interviewed by Ivo Ribeiro, Centro de Pesquisas Ellen G. White, Engenheiro Coelho, São Paulo, November 28, 2017.?
3. Nilson S. Ferreira, "Vida e Obras do Professor Pedro Apolinário" (Monografia, Instituto Adventista de Ensino, 1987), 5.?
4. Ferreira, 5-6; Décio Apolinário, interviewed by Ivo Ribeiro, Centro de Pesquisas Ellen G. White, Engenheiro Coelho, São Paulo, November 28, 2017.?
5. Ferreira, 6.?
6. "Pedro Apolinário," *Revista Adventista*, February 2006, 37. ?
7. Ferreira, 5; Décio Apolinário, interviewed by Ivo Ribeiro, Centro de Pesquisas Ellen G. White, Engenheiro Coelho, São Paulo, November 28, 2017.?
8. Rubens S. Lessa, "Ânimo e fé durante o sequestro," *Revista Adventista*, year 87, no. 7, July 1991, 5; Décio Apolinário, interviewed by Ivo Ribeiro, Centro de Pesquisas Ellen G. White, Engenheiro Coelho, São Paulo, November 28, 2017.?
9. Lessa, 5.?
10. Fabiana Marinello, "Fundador do grupo Apolinário morre aos 82 anos," *Diário do Grande ABC*, March 30, 2000, accessed November 23, 2017, [http://www.dgabc.com.br/Noticia/174207/fundador-do-grupo-apolinario-morre-aos-82-anos.?](http://www.dgabc.com.br/Noticia/174207/fundador-do-grupo-apolinario-morre-aos-82-anos.)
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"Nossa História - A história de um colégio abençoado por Deus - Colégio Adventista de Taubaté-Tremembé," Portal Educação Adventista, accessed November 23, 2017, [http://taubate.educacaoadventista.org.br/sobre.](http://taubate.educacaoadventista.org.br/sobre;); and Décio Apolinário, interviewed by Ivo Ribeiro, Centro de Pesquisas Ellen G. White, Engenheiro Coelho, São Paulo, November 28, 2017.?

12. Fabiana Marinello, "Fundador do grupo Apolinário morre aos 82 anos," Diário do Grande ABC, March 30, 2000, accessed November 23, 2017, [http://www.dgabc.com.br/Noticia/174207/fundador-do-grupo-apolinario-morre-aos-82-anos.?](http://www.dgabc.com.br/Noticia/174207/fundador-do-grupo-apolinario-morre-aos-82-anos.)
13. Décio Apolinário, interviewed by Ivo Ribeiro, Centro de Pesquisas Ellen G. White, Engenheiro Coelho, São Paulo, November 28, 2017.

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"Pedro Apolinário," *Revista Adventista*, February 2006, 37. Accessed February 26, 2018. [http://acervo.revistaadventista.com.br/.](http://acervo.revistaadventista.com.br/)

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